

Revalidation of *Stagmomantis* (*Stagmomantis*) *conspurcata* (Serville, 1839)

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Stagmomantis carolina represents one of the most taxonomically confounded species among New World Mantodea. The multiple taxonomic permutations that this species has undergone over the past two centuries are staggering and have largely been based upon individual variation of the mosaic array of color forms that are represented within this species. Since the first recorded specimen was sent to Carl Linné in 1763 from a collector in the New World colony of “Carolina,” there have been several intraspecific variants that were collected from the United States and named as distinct species. Most of these names were correctly synonymized in the early 1900s but since then, *carolina* has turned into a taxonomic dumping ground where this name has been attributed to multiple Nearctic and Neotropical species and, to compensate for the disparate populations all lumped together as one, *carolina* has been regarded as an extremely variable species in both pigmentation and morphology with a wide distribution range throughout the western hemisphere.

Rodrigues initiated a phylogenetic study of Mantidae in 2018 to better clarify the subfamily relationships within this family of common Mantodea. Although the final determinations of this study are pending, preliminary data regarding the members of *Stagmomantis* has shown that *carolina*, a species long conceptualized as having a massive distribution range extending from New Jersey to Argentina, is in fact endemic to the Eastern United States. Through personal correspondence with the author regarding his analysis of male *Stagmomantis* genitalia in 2019, Rodrigues asserted his belief that “*Stagmomantis carolina* should be restricted to east coast only. The specimens from Southern USA/Northern Mexico are a second species and the specimens from southern Central America a third species.”

Due to this newfound endemism of *carolina*, it is necessary to reevaluate the previous names that have been historically synonymized with this species. Regarding those species with type localities from the United States, all but two are to be upheld as true synonyms. These two exceptions include *conspurcata* Serville, 1839 and *simplex* Giglio-Tos, 1917, which are both believed to represent the same species from the Southern United

States/northern Mexico region that Rodrigues delineated as being distinct based upon his genitalia analysis.

In 1839, Serville described *Mantis conspurcata* from a male specimen that had been collected in “Amérique septentrionale” and given to him from a Mr. Leroux of Rouen, France. It is unclear whether Mr. Leroux had actually collected the specimen himself or what part of the territory it was obtained from or precisely when. What is more certain, however, is that this specimen derived from the United States, as “Amérique septentrionale” (“Northern America” in English) is the antiquated French designation for the land area north of the Americas that does not include Mexico, as opposed to the modern North America distinction that includes the land area from Mexico to Canada. Given that the type specimen remained in the possession of a French citizen provides further support to its derivation being from the colonial United States, most likely that of the Louisiana Territory, an area that was occupied by France until the 1760s, rather than Mexico, which was occupied by Spain during this time period.

Serville described the male *conspurcata* specimen as having hyaline forewings with “a number of irregular points, blackish, widespread without order, some of which are but atoms”. He went on to note that the hindwings are “transparent in all their extent; their first third colorless, having towards the end some scattered points, roughly like those of the elytra; the last two thirds of the wings blackish, loaded with a large number of transverse veins, whitish.” These characters, in conjunction with the measurements of the body and pronotum offered within Serville’s original description, detail a specimen that is considerably larger and with much lighter wing maculation than of those *carolina* found in the Eastern U.S. Further, Serville’s description of *conspurcata* perfectly aligns with the larger, less maculated “*carolina*” specimens found within Texas and parts of the Southern U.S.

Scudder synonymized *conspurcata* with *carolina* in his 1900 catalogue of described Orthoptera with no justification or commentary for the action. Seventeen years later, in 1917, Giglio-Tos described *Stagmomantis simplex* based upon a female specimen from Texas and a male from Mexico. Giglio-Tos described the male hindwings of *simplex* as having infumated tessellation in the posterior half of the anal area in addition to possessing morphological measurements that were significantly larger than those of *carolina*. In 1935, Beier synonymized *simplex* with *carolina*, and just like Scudder’s earlier synonymization of *conspurcata*, there was no documented rationale for this action. Thus, the historical record presents us with two names of a *Stagmomantis* species found in the United States, both presumed from the Texas/Louisiana region, that are described as being significantly larger and having much lighter maculation than *carolina*. Both of these species were subsequently synonymized with *carolina* with no justification. As the descriptions of Giglio-Tos’ *simplex* and Serville’s *conspurcata* align with current representatives of the morphologically and genetically distinct population of *Stagmomantis* that presently occurs in the southern US/northern Mexico region, it is proposed that these names are the appropriate designation for this population. Therefore, *conspurcata* should be reinstated as a valid species to demarcate this population from that

of *carolina* and given that *conspurcata* was the earlier name of the two, *simplex* should be considered its junior synonym.

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) conspurcata (Serville, 1839) **stat. rev.**
= *Stagmomantis simplex* Giglio-Tos, 1917 **n. syn.**

Diagnosis. Habitus moderate in size. Male body length measuring 51-66, pronotum length 17-21, forewing length 35-43 mm. Female body length measuring 57-67, pronotum length 21- 26, forewing length 23-27 mm. Male forewings typically lightly maculated with scattered, rounded tessellation to entirely hyaline. Male hindwings most often maculated only in posterior third, apical one-fourth of discoidal area lightly maculated to entirely clear. Female abdomen subcylindrical to subfusiform, margins nearly equal in width throughout to slightly widened. Distributed throughout lower Midwest, Texas, and Gulf Coast regions of the United States into Mexico.

In comparison to the type species *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) carolina* (Linné, 1763), *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) conspurcata* **stat. rev.** differs by having significantly larger body dimensions and lightly maculated to entirely hyaline wings. Further, *conspurcata* occupies a different ecoregion and elevation strata within the country. Whereas *carolina* occurs within the East Coast and higher elevations of the Midwest, *conspurcata* occurs throughout the lowland regions of the lower Midwest, Texas, and Gulf Coast, ranging into northern Mexico.

References. Linné (1763) pgs 13-14; Serville (1839) pgs 190-191; Scudder (1900) pg 12; Giglio-Tos (1917) pg 54; Giglio-Tos (1927) pgs 379-380; Beier (1935) pg 95; Hebard (1942) pgs 283-285; Anderson (2019) pgs 154-167

Species Photographs. *Stagnomantis conspurcata*: A, male dorsal habitus. League City, Galveston Co, TX 09.04.17; B, male dorsal habitus. Sweeny, Brazoria Co, TX 09.15.17

Species Photographs. *Stagmomantis conspurcata*: C, female dorsal habitus. Sweeney, Brazoria Co, TX 10.31.18; D, female dorsal habitus. Pecos River, Val Verde Co, TX 09.18.87

Species Photographs. E, *Stagnomantis carolina* female (left) vs *Stagnomantis conspurcata* female (right)

F

Species Photographs. F, *Stagmomantis carolina* male (left) vs *Stagmomantis conspurcata* male (right)

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) conspurcata (Serville, 1839) **stat. rev.**

Description. Habitus of moderate size, slender in males, more robust in females. General coloration green to greenish-brown, brown, tan, or various tones of gray.

Head capsule. Triangular, broad, vertex nearly straight, equal in elevation to dorsal surface of compound eyes. Lower frons broad, spanning nearly twice as wide as tall, superior margin broadly obtuse-angulate. Compound eyes large, protruding, smooth, ovoid-globular, pigmented same as body color. Male ocelli quite salient, shining, those of female inconspicuous. Male antennae elongate, setaceous, nearly reaching base of metazona. Female antennae reaching into distal third of metazona, moniliform. Antennae dark brownish-black in both sexes. Head capsule colored same as body color.

Pronotum. Elongated, slender, measuring longer than forecoxae. Supracoxal dilation marked with distal portion of metazona gradually conforming into expansion. Metazona approximately 3.5 times longer than prozona with low medial keel. Margins of metazona subparallel. Prozona consistently wider than metazona but not surpassing supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins weakly armed with dark denticles in both sexes; metazonal margins weakly denticulate in female, smooth in male. Coloration of pronotum typically uniformly green to greenish-brown, brown, tan or gray with variable amount of darker punctation. Light phase individuals may have extensive violet shading throughout metazona.

Prothoracic legs. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae armed with 5-9 uniform-sized, blackish denticles, between which are small serrations of same color as coxae, all of which much more pronounced and stout in female. Posteroventral margin of forecoxae with sparse, minute denticulation. Exterior surface of forecoxae solid green, light brownish to gray, with 3 irregular darker brown bands of varying intensity in darker phased individuals. Interior surface greenish to faint violet in dark phase. Both sexes with base of forecoxae and surrounding prosternum area blackened in addition to having brownish-black blotch at distal end in all color phases. Forefemora bear 4 posteroventral, 13-16 anteroventral, and 4 discoidal spines, all of which are entirely brownish-black; tibial spur groove placed in distal half. External surface of forefemora patterned similar to forecoxae by being either solid green, brown, or gray with 3 contrasting bands of darker coloration in dark phase. Internal surface of forefemora most often with darkened blotches near trochanter, base of discoidal spines, and tibial spur groove. Foretibiae approximately half the length of forefemora, bearing 9-11 posteroventral and 11-14 anteroventral spines. Pigmentation same as body color with black tips.

Meso/metathoracic legs. Slender, smooth, predominantly pigmented same color as body in female, usually green regardless of body color in males. Meso/metathoracic coxae and base of femora occasionally pigmented violet in light phase individuals. Dark phase individuals may have faint annulations on meso/metathoracic femora toward apices.

Wings. Male forewings long, narrow, extending slightly past abdomen. Discoidal area nearly immaculate with light scattering of small, roundish, brownish-black maculations. Light phase individuals often with discoidal area entirely hyaline, save the stigma; dark phase individuals have greater concentration of maculation but spots remain isolated, not mottled. Costal area narrow, measuring roughly one-fifth total width of forewing, entirely hyaline to very sparsely maculated with few small spots. Stigma

typically salient, black, usually much darker than other scant maculation present about the discoidal area, rarely reduced. Female forewings opaque, narrow, extending to abdominal tergite IV-V. Green phase individuals typically have pigmentation of forewings solid green, occasionally with thin whitish margin. Forewings of darker phased individuals are often densely mottled with various shades of brown, green, and gray with small amounts of blackish maculations throughout. Costal area spans one-fourth the width of entire forewing. Apices as broad as base, rounded. Stigma generally black and conspicuous, roundish, surrounded by whitish-tan blotch in light phased individuals, occasionally faded. Jugal lobe hyaline to heavily infumated. Male hindwings slightly shorter than forewings. Discoidal area immaculate. Anal area largely hyaline with either sparse scattering of spots toward posterior half in light phase to short rows of maculation radiating from posterior margin in dark phase. Female hindwings somewhat exceeding apices of forewings, often extending into next tergite. Anal area of hindwings most often with solid yellow base and tessellated with bands of lemon yellow cubes against hyaline field. Dark phase individuals typically have anal area deeply infumated with yellowish-white transverse veins. Discoidal area yellow, reddish, or light orange. Apices yellowish to greenish or infumated with varying degrees of black.

Abdomen. Male abdomen slender, elongated, pigmented entirely reddish-brown. Female abdomen subfusiform with widest dilation at tergite V. Coloration same as body with variable degree of mottling in dark phase individuals that often concentrates into darkened lateral blotches along tergites IV-VII. Light phase individuals may have yellowish cast to abdominal tergites, whereas darker phase individuals may have tergites tinged golden brown. Pleura pigmented greenish to purplish-gray.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 51-66; pronotum length 17-21; forewing length 35-43; prothoracic coxa length 9-11; prothoracic femur length 11-14; metathoracic femur length 11-15. *Female.* Body length 57-67; pronotum length 21-26; forewing length 23-27; prothoracic coxa length 13-14; prothoracic femur length 15-17; metathoracic femur length 15-17.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are fairly robust, elongate-oval in shape, measuring 7-11 mm wide, 14-28 mm long, and 12-13 mm tall. Distal end slightly concave with short amount of residual process extending away from base; proximal end broadly rounded. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 14-25 egg chambers. External wall golden brown in color with wide, raised, whitish-tan emergence area consisting of 28-32 teardrop-shaped openings placed alternately down center of dorsal surface. These openings are sealed with dried froth until nymph emergence. Emergence area often margined by darker reddish-brown, giving ootheca banded appearance. *Oothecae* are attached along their entire ventral surface so that they sit with the dorsal surface exposed and thus the emergence area is parallel to the substrate. Oviposition sites include woody plant stems, thick twigs, and tree bark in addition to a variety of artificial vertical surfaces such as building walls and fences.

Development. Nymphs will emerge within 50-60 days if not exposed to the cold; otherwise a 2 month diapause occurs over the cooler, winter months. Nymph emergence is synchronized and generally takes place during early morning hours. Proto-nymphs molt embryonic cuticle after threading 3-7 mm past emergence flaps. First instar nymphs will then quickly disperse away from the ootheca and their siblings. Nymphs resemble adults in form and coloration, especially toward later instars. First instar nymphs are

greenish in color, gradually turning greenish-brown or brownish within hours of emergence. Younger instar nymphs range in color from green, gray, or brown, with limbs maintaining greenish hue regardless of body color. Legs are typically darkly annulated during early instars, these bands often fading during maturity. Older instar nymphs demonstrate wider array of color variations and mottling as exhibited by adults, especially during final instar. First instar nymphs will begin taking water from droplets within the first day of their emergence. Thereafter they begin feeding upon small prey items, including conspecifics. Older instar nymphs are also highly cannibalistic and will commonly attack prey much larger than themselves. Maturation takes between 66-111 days. Females undergo 7 (rarely 8-9) instars of development and males undergo 6 before reaching adulthood with an average instar period of 13 days, depending on nutritional intake.

Adulthood. Adults of this species may be found throughout the year but predominantly occur between September and October. Adult males typically die off several weeks prior to females and are far less scarce from late fall into the following summer. This species is bivoltine with overlapping generations during the winter months when both adults and nymphs co-occur. Adults of both sexes, as well as nymphs, are encountered among flowering weeds, low bushes, and other vegetation within gardens, fields, and forest undergrowth.

Reproduction. Females readily mate 1-3 days after their final molt. Males demonstrate interest in mating 3-5 days after their final molt. Mature males will visually track receptive females for a few seconds to several minutes before rapidly pouncing upon them, which may evoke aggression from the female. Rarely will males stalk the female for an hour or more. Males typically mount the female from behind and may remain clinging to her for several hours before copulating. Mating generally lasts for 6-8 hours but occasionally spans 1-2 days. Multiple males may mount a female simultaneously but only one can engage in copulation. Cannibalism during mating occasionally occurs with most well fed females showing no aggression throughout the process. Surviving males will typically fly away once mating is concluded. Males may also remain mounted to the female after copulation has been discontinued, which further endangers them to cannibalism regardless of the female's appetite. Unmated males will usually perish approximately 1 month after final molt regardless. Oviposition generally takes place at night. Females will continue to produce a new ootheca every 3-25 days after their first oviposition, depending on food availability and repeated mating. Mated females are capable of producing up to 14 oothecae that contain between 60-140 eggs each before succumbing to age after approximately 4 months of life. When multiple oothecae are generated, those that are produced toward the end of the female's life tend to be smaller and are more likely to be infertile. Unmated females will produce infertile oothecae between 25-30 days after final molt. These infertile oothecae are of roughly the same size and shape as viable ones.

Ethology. Adult males are attracted to lights at night and are, in general, much more active than females. Adult females will first respond to threats by remaining motionless. If threat persists, females may respond with a deimatic display that involves facing the aggressor, unfurling both wings above body, partial abdominal dorsiflexion and outward or partial extension of forelegs. Interestingly, older nymphs may also occasionally employ a similar deimatic display despite not having developed wings.

Adult males will demonstrate a deimatic display like that of the adult female but will more often flee or take to flight in initial response to threats. Mature females are quite aggressive and will actively pursue nearby prey, often of equivalent or slightly larger body size.

Narrative. This species occurs throughout the lowland regions of the lower Midwest, Texas, and Gulf Coast, ranging into northern Mexico. It is restricted from inhabiting upper latitude areas of the United States with corresponding higher elevations, where it is replaced by *carolina* in the East and *limbata* in the West.

References. Linné (1763) pgs 13-14; Serville (1839) pgs 190-191; Giglio-Tos (1917) pg 54; Giglio-Tos (1927) pgs 379-380; Beier (1935) pg 95; Breland (1941) pg 176; Hebard (1942) pgs 283-285; Saw (2011) pgs 5-43; Anderson (2019) pgs 168-181; Rodrigues (2019) pers. comm.

01, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult male. Brazoria, Brazoria Co, TX 09.06.15

02, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult male. Dallas, Dallas Co, TX 09.16.14

03, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* male deimatic display. Moss Bluff, Calcasieu Co, LA 08.18.18

04, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult female. Bear Creek, Travis Co, TX 09.03.17

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult male

Photographed by Monica Krancevic

02, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult male

Photographed by Annika Lindqvist

03, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* male deimatic display

Photographed by Shannon Foreman

04, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* adult female

Photographed by Blake Hendon

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